

SIGMA: a software tool to simulate non-stationary ground motions for engineering applications

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Abstract: The selection of the input ground motion is becoming more and more important in the framework of earthquake engineering. Simulated ground motion time series can be a valid alternative to natural ground motions, which can be scarce for certain combinations of earthquake scenario and site conditions, especially for large, infrequent earthquakes. The simulated records can be used for applications in nonlinear dynamic analyses of civil structures. This work presents a new Matlab-based software tool that allows to generate a chosen number of simulated ground motions given few input parameters, namely Magnitude, Distance, $V_{s,30}$ and Style of Faulting. The time series are simulated with an up-to-date non-stationary stochastic model which was calibrated using the empirical ground motion model (GMM) based on the latest version of the Italian Strong Motion database ITACA. The simulated accelerograms show a good match with the GMM in terms of response and Fourier spectra, PGA and Arias Intensity.

Keywords: accelerograms; seismic input; response spectrum; software; seismic analyses;

1. Introduction

Ground motion records are widely used in earthquake engineering, especially to carry out nonlinear analyses in the time domain. Seismic codes (EC8, 2008) require the use of a number of accelerograms to perform structural analyses. The increasing availability of large strong motion databases pushes toward the use of natural accelerograms. However, natural records corresponding to the desired combination of magnitude, distance, soil type and SOF are not always available. To overcome this issue, a number of methods and techniques were proposed for generating accelerograms. A detailed review of the different techniques for predicting earthquake ground motions for engineering purposes is provided in Douglas and Aochi (2008).

In this work, we propose a new Matlab-based software tool (SIGMA: SIMulation of Ground Motions for engineering Applications) which allows to generate a number N of simulated ground motion time series. The application was created for engineering applications, so the end-users it is not needed to have a strong background in engineering seismology concepts and it requires four input parameters only in order to define the target earthquake scenario: magnitude, source to site distance, shear wave velocity in the uppermost 30 m at the site, and style of faulting.

The application is based on the simulation method proposed by Sabetta et al. (2021), which updates the non-stationary stochastic model initially proposed by Sabetta and Pugliese (1996 – SP96). Some improvements to the method were later proposed by other authors (Pousse 2006; Laurendeau 2012). The methodology proposed in Sabetta et al. (2021) is simple to implement, fast, and considers the basic concepts of seismology (Brune's source model, realistic time envelope function, non-stationarity in frequency, ground-motion variability). The four model parameters required for the simulation are obtained from regression analyses on a strong motion dataset of shallow active crustal events in Italy (Lanzano et al. 2019 – ITA18) and are embedded in the simulation code: Arias intensity (IA), significant duration

(DV), central frequency (F_c), and frequency bandwidth (F_b). The strong motion dataset was extracted from the large strong-motion databases Engineering Strong Motion database ESM 2.0 (<https://esm-db.eu>; Luzi et al. 2020) and the Italian ACcelerometric Archive ITACA 3.1 (<http://itaca.mi.ingv.it>; D'Amico et al. 2020). As mentioned above, time-domain simulations are derived from a time-frequency decomposition of the signal and depend on the above-mentioned parameters obtained from the Ground Motion Model (GMM) of ITA18. It follows that the results obtained with the application are specific for Italy, although the approach is general and can be adapted to other databases if predictive equations for Arias intensity and significant duration are available.

The aim of the proposed software tool (SIGMA) is to provide an easy-to-use, user-friendly graphical user interface (GUI) that allows to obtain acceleration time series consistent with the physical properties of real ground motion records, to be used in earthquake engineering applications. After a brief introduction of the methodology, the application will be presented and its main features will be explained. Then, some results in terms of acceleration, velocity time series and response spectra will be provided.

2. Methodology

Earthquake ground motions can be decomposed using time-frequency functions, such as time-varying power spectral density (PSD) functions (Sabetta and Pugliese 1996, Conte and Peng 1997) or the S-transform (Stockwell et al. 1996, Cui and Hong, 2020). This time-frequency decomposition can be fitted by a lognormal function defined through three parameters derived from the theory of the spectral moments (Vanmarcke, 1980; Lai, 1982): the average total power P_a , equal to the area under the PSD; the central frequency F_c , giving a measure of where the PSD is concentrated along the frequency axis; and the frequency bandwidth F_b , which corresponds to the dispersion of PSD around the central frequency. By inserting the time dependence and substituting PSD with $X_s(t,f)$, the definition of the spectral moments and of the relative parameters becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda_i(t) &= \int f^i X_s(t, f) df, \quad i = 0, 1, 2; \\ Pa(t) &= \lambda_0(t) \\ F_c(t) &= \lambda_1(t) / \lambda_0(t) \\ F_b(t) &= [\lambda_2(t) / \lambda_0(t) - F_c^2(t)]^{1/2}\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where $Pa(t)$, instantaneous average power, is the time envelope function describing the amplitude variation of the ground motion. Its integral in the time domain is equal to the integral of $X_s(t,f)$ in the time-frequency plane and corresponds to the Arias Intensity (Arias, 1970, hereafter IA) in cm^2/s^3 apart from the scale factor $\pi/2g$:

$$I_A = \int x(t)^2 dt = \iint X_s(t, f) dt df = \int Pa(t) dt\tag{2}$$

$F_c(t)$, central frequency, and $F_b(t)$, frequency bandwidth, represent the non-stationarity of the frequency content and correspond, respectively, to the centroid of X_s and to the radius of gyration of X_s with respect to F_c in the frequency plane. With the above-defined parameters, it is possible to derive a lognormal function approximating $X_s(t,f)$:

$$\widetilde{X}_s(t, f) = \frac{Pa(t)}{f\sqrt{2\pi}\delta} e^{-[\ln f - \ln \beta(t)]^2 / 2\delta^2}\tag{3}$$

where $\beta(t)$ and δ are derived from $F_c(t)$ and $F_b(t)$ in the following way:

$$\ln \beta(t) = \ln F_c(t) - \delta^2 / 2\tag{4}$$

$$\delta = \sqrt{\ln[1 + F_b^2(t) / F_c^2(t)]}$$

The X_S function adopted in this study includes also Brune's ω -square spectrum with the aim to enrich the frequency spectrum at low frequencies, and it is equal to the lognormal function reported in Equation 3 for $f > f_m$ and to the arithmetic mean of the lognormal function $\widetilde{X}_s(t, f)$ and the ω -square Brune spectrum for $f < f_m$, where f_m is the frequency corresponding to the maximum value of the lognormal function. The Brune ω -square spectrum is defined as (Boore, 2003; Pousse, 2006):

$$\Omega(f) = \frac{(2\pi f)^2}{1+(f/f_c)^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\log_{10} f_c = 1.341 + \log_{10} \left(\beta (\Delta\sigma^{1/3}) \right) - 0.5M \quad (6)$$

where f_c is the corner frequency, $\Delta\sigma$ is the stress drop in bars, M is the moment magnitude, and β is the shear-wave velocity in km/s. The adopted values are $\Delta\sigma = 50$ bars and $\beta = 3.5$ km/s (Bindi & Kotha, 2020).

The modified function $\widetilde{X}'_s(t, f)$ is thus equal to:

$$\widetilde{X}'_s(t, f) = \begin{cases} \text{mean}[\Omega(f), \widetilde{X}_s(t, f)] & \text{if } f \leq f_m \\ \widetilde{X}_s(t, f) & \text{if } f > f_m \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 1 shows the fit of the spectral densities corresponding to ground motion recorded at the station of CSC (Cascia) during the Central Italy earthquake ($M_w = 6.5$) of October 30, 2016. The figure shows the PSD at time $t = 5$ s, with the modified lognormal described above and derived from the spectral moments of the corresponding time history (Eq. 1). It is evident the increase in low frequency content with respect to the former model of SP96 and the good fit of the modified lognormal with the PSD of the real record.

Fig. 1 Fit of the PSD for CSC record ($M_w = 6.5$) at time $t = 5$ s (red line). with the original lognormal function adopted by SP96 (dashed line) and the modified function adopted in this work (black solid line). For comparison, the normalized square of the Brune model for $M_w = 6.5$ is also shown (dotted line).

The Ground Motion Model ITA18 has been recently calibrated by Lanzano et al. (2019), using a dataset with 5607 records, 146 events and 1657 stations, for a magnitude range 3.5-8.0 from Italian and well-sampled worldwide earthquakes. The exhaustive description of Ground Motion Model of ITA18 is provided in Lanzano et al. 2019, while the particular choices made for the generation of simulated accelerograms are given in Sabetta et al. 2021. Regression analyses were performed on the dataset to determine the coefficients for the

predictive equation used to define the Arias Intensity (AI) and Vanmarcke Duration (DV), as well as for $F_c(t)$ and $F_b(t)$.

Regarding the $P_a(t)$, the method uses a time envelope which includes the contribution of P, S and Coda waves. Fig. 2 shows the graphical definition of the envelope function $P_a(t)$ proposed in this study in comparison with that adopted in SP96, together with an example of simulated ground motion time series.

Fig.2 (top) time envelope function $P_a(t)$ proposed in this study in case of $M_w=5$, $R_{JB}=10$ km and $V_{s,30}=600$ m/s; (b) corresponding simulated accelerogram.

The simulation of the accelerograms is then performed summing Fourier series with time-dependent coefficients derived from the function \widetilde{X}_S' (Eq. 6) as follows:

$$a(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N C_n(t) \cos(n2\pi f_0 t + \varphi_n) \quad (8)$$

$$C_n(t) = \sqrt{2\pi f_0 \widetilde{X}_S'(f_n, t)} \quad (9)$$

3. Computer code and GUI to simulate ground motions

Mathworks - Matlab® was used to create the software application SIGMA graphical user interface (GUI), which is displayed in Fig.3. The software application is freely available at the provided [link](#). As mentioned above, it requires four input parameters to run:

1. Magnitude: the magnitude parameter used is the moment magnitude (M_w). This was chosen according to the GMM of ITA18.
2. Distance: the user can choose between two types of source-to-site distance: the first is R_{JB} , which is defined as the closest horizontal distance to the vertical projection of the rupture as defined by Joyner & Boore (Abrahamson and Shedlock, 1997), and is the one employed in ITA18 to develop the GMM. The second is the epicentral distance R_{epi} , which is introduced given that this is most common in engineering applications. If R_{epi} is chosen, this is evaluated from R_{JB} according to the procedure suggested by Scherbaum et al. (2004), assuming a focal depth of 10 km for the sake of simplicity.

3. $V_{S,30}$: shear wave velocity in the uppermost 30 m at the site.
4. Fault Type: Normal, Thrust or Strike Slip.

The user is free to choose the number of records. The generation velocity is in the order of 0.5 seconds per accelerogram, so that it requires around 10 seconds to generate 10 accelerograms on an Intel® i7 computer with a CPU of 2.70GHz. When the user hits the button “run” the application displays a figure, showing the mean response spectrum of simulated ground motions including the standard deviation (sim.+ σ and sim.- σ), the mean value given by the adopted GMM with the boundaries of -10% and +30%. Then, the user is asked to choose the destination folder of the output files, and a number N of .txt files with progressive names (ACC₁,... ACC_i,... ACC_N) is saved to the chosen folder. Each .txt file is a single column file containing the acceleration amplitudes of the generated ground motion records, in cm/s² units. The records have a time step of 0.005 s.

Fig. 3 GUI of the software to generate simulated ground motions (SIGMA, version 1.0)

4. Results

An example of results generated by the SIGMA application is reported in Fig. 4. The figure shows the simulated time series in terms of acceleration (top) and velocity (middle) for two different generations in the same run. The most important remark can be done on the response spectra: it is possible to observe that even the response spectrum of the single simulated time series has a good agreement with the spectrum predicted with the ground motion model ITA18 using the same parameters.

Fig. 4 Two examples of simulated ground motion records in terms of acceleration (top) and velocities time series, and comparison of the response spectra of the simulated accelerogram and ITA18, respectively for $M_W=6.5$, $R_{JB}=10$ km, $V_{S,30}=600$ and for Normal Fault style.

From Fig. 4 it is also possible to notice the variability included in the simulated time series. The variability depends on the introduction of random phases in the time series, and in addition for each simulated ground motion the value of the duration DV is chosen randomly using the standard deviation values provided by the ground motion model. This variability can be observed in Table 1 and Table 2 for several scenarios in terms of magnitude distance and site conditions. The variability of 100 simulations as a percentage, calculated as $(\max - \min)/\min$ is around 60% for Arias Intensity, 120% and for PGA. The coefficient of variation is instead around 9% for Arias, 16% for PGA.

Table 1. Arias Intensity resulting from 100 simulations for different scenarios compared with the values predicted by the GMM of Lanzano et al. (ITA18). CV (%) is the coefficient of variation in percentage. Var (%) is the variability calculated as $100 * (\max - \min) / \min$.

	$M_W=5$ $R_{JB}=10$ km $V_{S,30}=400$ m/s	$M_W=6.5$ $R_{JB}=30$ km $V_{S,30}=800$ m/s	$M_W=6.0$ $R_{JB}=50$ km $V_{S,30}=600$ m/s	$M_W=7$ $R_{JB}=5$ km $V_{S,30}=800$ m/s
	ARIAS (cm^2/s^3)			
Mean	1485	2710	354	71799
CV (%)	11.0	8.9	7.3	8.7
Min	1147	2129	271	54609
Max	1900	3265	443	86159
Var (%)	66	53	63	58
ITA18	1493	2728	358	72477

Table 2. PGA resulting from 100 simulations for different scenarios compared with the values predicted by the GMM of Lanzano et al. (ITA18). CV (%) is the coefficient of variation in percentage. Var (%) is the variability calculated as $100*(max-min)/min$.

	PGA (cm/s ²)			
Mean	49.7	50.7	16.5	306.1
CV (%)	19.3	16.6	13.3	15.3
Min	34.8	37.8	11.6	219.4
Max	79.1	88.1	22.3	466.6
Var (%)	127	134	92	113
ITA18	60.4	52.4	17.7	317.8

Fig. 5 reports four simulated records for $M_w=6$, $R_{epi}=20$ km, $V_{s,30}=600$ and Normal Fault style. For a single combination of parameters, it is possible to notice the variation both in the amplitude modulation in time and in terms of total duration of the record. For example if the record in the right panel are considered, the top one has a duration of 22.3 s, while the second one reaches 24.5 seconds.

Fig. 5. Simulated time series for $M_w=6$, $R_{epi}=20$ km, $V_{s,30}=600$, Normal Fault style.

The attenuation of the simulated accelerograms with the distance from the source is represented in Fig. 6, in case of strike-slip fault, $V_{s,30}=400$ m/s, $M_w=6$, and $R_{JB}=10$, 30, and 50 km, respectively. As expected, larger distances correspond to smaller accelerations and longer durations.

Fig. 7 compares the acceleration response spectra of ten simulated accelerograms with the 50-percentile spectrum predicted by ITA18. As comparison criterion we chose, in accordance with the Italian Seismic Code NTC18 (D.M., 2018) and the Eurocode EC8 (CEN, 2009), a tolerance range of -10% and +30% with respect to the target spectrum. The red dotted lines in the figure correspond to the above-mentioned limits respect to ITA18. The black dashed lines represent the bound of \pm one standard deviation of the seven simulations.

Fig. 6 Simulated accelerograms in case of strike-slip fault, $V_{S,30}=400$ m/s, $M = 6$, and RJB equal to: (a) 10, (b) 30, and (c) 50 km.

The fit is quite satisfactory even for such a small number of simulations. In this release of the software tool, the variability of the simulated spectra is only due to the different phases of the corresponding time series and the duration, while it does not consider the uncertainty in the prediction of the ground-motion parameters used for the simulation (i.e. Arias Intensity), which will be considered in the next works. Nevertheless, it has to be highlighted that the simulation method is capable of matching adequately the target response spectrum, even with a small number of simulations.

Fig. 7. Response spectra of ten simulated accelerograms compared with the spectrum predicted by ITA18 GMM, in case of normal fault, $M_w = 6.5$, $R_{JB}=10$ km, $V_{S,30}=600$ m/s;

5. Code-based evaluation of seismic input for engineering applications

The relatively easy and fast generation of simulated records, compatible with an assigned design spectrum is still very popular for both practice and research purposes (Iervolino et al. 2010b). Little guidance is provided by EC8 on how to select/generate code-compatible time-series, therefore several articles have proposed sets of accelerograms consistent with the standard EC8 spectra (e.g. Giaralis and Spanos, 2011; Iervolino et al., 2010b). Iervolino et al. (2010b) evaluated the nonlinear response of three types of SDOF systems applying different methods to generate artificial and simulated time series as well as scaled natural records. The main challenge when spectrum-compatible accelerograms are generated is to preserve the consistency with the original seismological parameters. In order to assess the variability in the response of engineering systems due to the differences in the simulated

input motions, Causse et al. (2014) used the ground motion simulation method proposed by Laurendeau et al. (2012), very similar to the methodology proposed here, and compute the nonlinear response of SDOF systems. They show that the non-stationary stochastic approach of generating accelerograms is quite useful in capturing the true ground-motion variability and consequently the variability of building response. To check the compatibility of the response spectra simulated with the method proposed in this study with the provisions of seismic codes, we compared the average spectra of 20 simulated ground motions with the spectral shapes given by the Eurocode EC8 (CEN, 2009). Fig. 8 shows the good agreement of the simulated spectra, normalized to their PGA, with the spectral shapes foreseen by EC8, type A soil, in case of high (Type 1) and low (Type 2) magnitudes. The M_w values of 7 and 5 correspond to those adopted (Sabetta and Bommer, 2002) for the calibration of EC8 type 1 and 2, respectively.

Fig. 8 Comparison of the mean of 20 simulated response spectra (normalized to the PGA) with (left) EC8 type 1 spectrum ($M_w=7$, $RJB=5$, $V_{S,30}=800$) and (right) EC8 Type 2 ($M_w=5$, $RJB=30$, $V_{S,30}=800$).

4. Conclusions

This work presents the novel Matlab-based software application SIGMA (Simulation of Ground Motions for engineering Applications), which allows to generate a chosen number of simulated ground motions given few input parameters, namely Magnitude, Distance, $V_{S,30}$ and Style of Faulting. The time series are simulated with an updated non-stationary stochastic model which was calibrated using the empirical ground motion model (GMM) based on the latest version of the Italian Strong Motion database. The simulated accelerograms show a good match with the GMM in terms of response and Fourier spectra, PGA, PGV and Arias Intensity. The methodology proposed in this paper can be adapted to different databases provided that regional GMMs for Arias intensity and significant duration are available. The software tool is capable of reproducing the non-stationarity in amplitude and frequency of natural recorded ground motions and their spectrum-compatibility with the response spectrum predicted by the ground motion model ITA18, thus it is promising for applications in dynamic analyses of structures in the time domain. The software application is easy to use by end-users with a basic knowledge of the concepts of seismology, it is efficient and fast.

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